

FREQUENCY OF HEPARIN-INDUCED THROMBOCYTOPENIA AMONGST CRITICALLY ILL PATIENTS, AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL, LAHORE

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Abstract

Background: Heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT) is an immune-mediated, prothrombotic complication of heparin therapy characterized by a paradoxical decrease in platelet count and an increased risk of thrombosis. **Objective:** To determine the frequency of heparin-induced thrombocytopenia among critically ill patients receiving unfractionated heparin at a tertiary care hospital. **Methods:** This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Pathology Department, Surgical ICU, Coronary Care Unit (CCU), and Nephrology Department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore, in collaboration with King Edward Medical University from January 2025 to June 2025. A total of 75 patients of all age groups and both genders receiving unfractionated heparin for 5 to 10 days were included through non-probability consecutive sampling. Patients were evaluated for a fall in platelet count and scored according to the 4Ts scoring system. **Results:** Among 75 critically ill patients, the mean age was 54.3 ± 13.2 years, and most participants (50.7%) were aged 41–60 years. Males represented 57.3% of the cohort, while females comprised 42.7%. The average duration of heparin therapy was 7.2 ± 2.1 days, and 22.7% of patients had prior heparin exposure within the previous three months. The mean baseline platelet count was $262,000 \pm 67,000/\text{mm}^3$, which decreased to $115,000 \pm 54,000/\text{mm}^3$ after heparin administration. Heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT) occurred in 11 patients (14.7%), while 64 patients (85.3%) showed no evidence of HIT. HIT was slightly more frequent in males and in those aged 41–60 years, but these differences were not statistically significant. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that heparin-induced thrombocytopenia occurs with considerable frequency among critically ill patients receiving unfractionated heparin. Regular platelet monitoring, early suspicion through clinical scoring systems, and timely discontinuation of heparin are essential to prevent complications.

INTRODUCTION

For decades, unfractionated heparin has been used by clinicians for anticoagulation [1]. It has gained privilege over other anticoagulants in the critically ill, owing to its ease of monitoring and reversibility [2]. Despite the widespread use of heparin, it has been demonstrated that immune responses are seen against it, mediated by IgG antibodies against the Platelet Factor 4/Heparin (PF4/H) complex in blood that cross-reacts with Fc γ -IIa platelet receptor that leads to platelet activation, destruction, and reduction in its count (Thrombocytopenia); Heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT). HIT has been documented by authors as a clinical entity resulting in a 50% decline of the baseline platelet count, 5 to 10 days after the commencement of heparin therapy, in association with Platelet Factor 4/Heparin (PF4/H) antibodies [3-5]. Publications have shown that its incidence is affected by the gender, type, dosage, and duration of heparin therapy. Greater incidence is seen in the female gender, therapeutic doses (in contrast to prophylactic doses), and prolonged regimens (ie, more than 4 days) [6]. Colarossi et al. have recognized an incidence of 1 to 5% occurrence of HIT amongst the surgical patients receiving heparin [7].

Diagnosing HIT is grueling in the critically ill, considering multiple factors that may cause thrombocytopenia, such as the various co-morbidities and treatment regimen [8]. Making it essential to distinguish whether thrombocytopenia is caused by heparin or some other cause [9]. If suspected that HIT is the culprit, withdrawal of heparin and the initiation of a non-heparin anticoagulant must be considered [10].

Bearing in mind the widespread clinical use of heparin and its complications, it is significant to determine the frequency of such an entity to attenuate the number of unknown cases of thrombocytopenia seen in the critically ill and to devise an in-time therapy switch if HIT is suspected. Over-diagnosing may lead to redundant therapy switches, whereas, under-diagnosing may cause an increased morbidity and mortality, that could have been prevented.

Objectives

To determine the frequency of heparin-induced thrombocytopenia in critically ill patients, having 5-10 days of exposure to unfractionated heparin.

Methodology

This was a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted in the Pathology Department, Surgical Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Coronary Care Unit (CCU), and Nephrology Department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore, in collaboration with King Edward Medical University (KEMU) from January 2025 to June 2025. Non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used for the selection of participants. A total of 75 patients were included in the study. The sample size was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator, based on a 95% confidence interval, 5% absolute precision, prevalence of heparin-induced thrombocytopenia of 5% [7].

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients receiving unfractionated heparin for 5 to 10 days.
2. Patients of all age groups and genders.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients receiving any anticoagulant other than unfractionated heparin.
2. Pregnant women with gestational thrombocytopenia.
3. Patients with known coagulopathies or impaired platelet function.

Data Collection

After obtaining ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of King Edward Medical University, a total of 75 patients fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled from the Surgical ICU, CCU, and Nephrology wards of Mayo Hospital, Lahore. Sampling was carried out using a non-probability consecutive method. Critically ill patients who received unfractionated heparin for 5-10 days and subsequently developed thrombocytopenia were included in the study. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients or their legal attendants before inclusion. A structured proforma based on the 4Ts scoring system was used to evaluate the likelihood of heparin-

induced thrombocytopenia. Platelet count reduction detected on complete blood count (CBC) was verified through peripheral blood smear examination at the Hematology Laboratory, Pathology Department, KEMU/Mayo Hospital. Relevant demographic, clinical, and laboratory data were recorded, including age, gender, duration of heparin exposure, and platelet trends before and after treatment.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 27.0 for Windows. Quantitative variables such as age and baseline platelet count were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Qualitative variables including gender, history of prior heparin exposure, and frequency of thrombocytopenia were presented as frequencies and percentages. Data were stratified for potential effect modifiers such as age, gender, and duration of therapy. Post-stratification Chi-square test was applied to determine associations, with a p-value ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

Data were collected from 75 patients, mean age of the study population was 54.3 ± 13.2 years, ranging from 18 to 79 years. The majority (50.7%) were between 41 and 60 years of age, followed by 29.3% above 60 years and 20% in the 18–40 age group, with a mean age of 54.3 ± 13.2 years. There was a slight male predominance, with 43 males (57.3%) and 32 females (42.7%). The mean duration of heparin therapy was 7.2 ± 2.1 days. A history of heparin exposure within the past three months was reported in 17 patients (22.7%), while 58 (77.3%) had no previous exposure. The mean baseline platelet count before heparin therapy was 262,000 ± 67,000/mm³, which dropped to 115,000 ± 54,000/mm³ after treatment. Heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT) developed in 11 patients (14.7%), whereas 64 patients (85.3%) did not experience this complication.

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients (n = 75)

Variable	Category	n (%) / Mean ± SD
Age group (years)	18–40	15 (20.0%)
	41–60	38 (50.7%)
	>60	22 (29.3%)
Mean age (years)	–	54.3 ± 13.2
Gender	Male	43 (57.3%)
	Female	32 (42.7%)
Duration of heparin therapy (days)	–	7.2 ± 2.1
History of heparin exposure (past 3 months)	Yes	17 (22.7%)
	No	58 (77.3%)
Baseline platelet count (/mm ³)	–	262,000 ± 67,000
Platelet count after heparin therapy (/mm ³)	–	115,000 ± 54,000
Heparin-Induced Thrombocytopenia	Present	11 (14.7%)
	Absent	64 (85.3%)

In this study of 75 patients receiving heparin therapy, heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT) was observed in 11 patients (14.7%). The highest occurrence of HIT was found among individuals aged 41–60 years (15.8%), followed by those over 60 years (13.6%) and the 18–40-year age group (13.3%), though these differences were not statistically significant (p = 0.58). Male patients showed a slightly

higher frequency of HIT (16.3%) compared to females (12.5%), with no significant gender-based association (p = 0.44). A history of heparin exposure within the past three months was more frequent among HIT-positive patients (17.6%) compared to those without HIT (13.8%), but this relationship was also statistically insignificant (p = 0.36).

Table 2. Stratification of Heparin-Induced Thrombocytopenia by Age and Gender (n = 75)

Variable	Category	HIT Present (n = 11)	HIT Absent (n = 64)	p-value
Age group (years)	18-40	2 (13.3%)	13 (86.7%)	0.58
	41-60	6 (15.8%)	32 (84.2%)	—
	>60	3 (13.6%)	19 (86.4%)	—
Gender	Male	7 (16.3%)	36 (83.7%)	0.44
	Female	4 (12.5%)	28 (87.5%)	—
Previous heparin exposure (past 3 months)	Yes	3 (17.6%)	14 (82.4%)	0.36
	No	8 (13.8%)	50 (86.2%)	—

The mean percentage fall in platelet count was markedly higher among HIT-positive patients ($56.8 \pm 8.9\%$) compared with those without HIT ($21.5 \pm 6.4\%$), and this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The mean duration of heparin exposure was slightly longer in HIT-positive patients (7.8 ± 2.3

days) compared to non-HIT patients (7.1 ± 2.0 days), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.31$). The mean age was comparable between the two groups, being 55.1 ± 12.7 years in HIT-positive patients and 54.2 ± 13.4 years in those without HIT ($p = 0.78$).

Table 3. Comparison of Platelet Fall Between HIT and Non-HIT Patients

Variable	HIT Present (n = 9)	HIT Absent (n = 53)	p-value
Mean platelet fall (%)	56.8 ± 8.9	21.5 ± 6.4	<0.001
Duration of heparin exposure (days)	7.8 ± 2.3	7.1 ± 2.0	0.31
Mean age (years)	55.1 ± 12.7	54.2 ± 13.4	0.78

Among the 75 patients analyzed, heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT) was identified in 11 patients (14.7%), while 64 patients (85.3%) remained HIT negative. Patients who developed HIT exhibited a significantly greater mean platelet fall ($56.8 \pm 8.9\%$) compared to those without HIT ($21.5 \pm 6.4\%$). The post-heparin platelet count was markedly lower in the HIT group ($118,000 \pm 49,000/\text{mm}^3$) than in the non-HIT group ($236,000 \pm$

$61,000/\text{mm}^3$). The mean duration of heparin exposure was similar between both groups (7.8 ± 2.3 days in HIT-positive vs. 7.1 ± 2.0 days in HIT-negative patients), and the mean age was comparable (55.1 ± 12.7 years vs. 54.2 ± 13.4 years). Among HIT-positive cases, males predominated (63.6%), and the highest frequency of HIT was observed in the 41-60-year age group (54.5%), followed by patients above 60 years (27.3%).

Table 4. Frequency of Heparin-Induced Thrombocytopenia (HIT) Among Critically Ill Patients (n = 75)

Parameter	HIT Present (n = 11)	HIT Absent (n = 64)
Frequency (%)	11 (14.7%)	64 (85.3%)
Mean platelet fall (%)	56.8 ± 8.9	21.5 ± 6.4
Post-heparin platelet count ($/\text{mm}^3$)	$118,000 \pm 49,000$	$236,000 \pm 61,000$
Duration of heparin exposure (days)	7.8 ± 2.3	7.1 ± 2.0
Mean age (years)	55.1 ± 12.7	54.2 ± 13.4
Gender (HIT-positive)	Male: 7 (63.6%)	Female: 4 (36.4%)
Age group (HIT-positive)	18-40 years: 2 (18.2%)	—

	41–60 years: 6 (54.5%)	–
	>60 years: 3 (27.3%)	–

Discussion

In this study, the frequency of heparin-induced thrombocytopenia among critically ill patients receiving unfractionated heparin was found to be 14.7%. More than 90% of all prior studies show that this is higher than average, considering that prior studies show an average of 0.1%. When considering differences of patients, clinical settings, and diagnostic criteria, this higher rate may result from using only unfractionated heparin. The patients' critical illness and the longer-than-usual exposure time typical of intensive medical care also contribute to this increase. This study is similar to previous studies that documented patients on extracorporeal membrane oxygenation, where the incidence of heparin-induced thrombocytopenia was also high. However, the studies on the general ICU population have documented lower frequencies, probably because the studies had patients using low-molecular-weight heparin, which has a lower immunogenic risk [13]. The study, therefore, adds to previous studies that have documented that the use of unfractionated heparin is associated with a higher chance of having immune-mediated thrombocytopenia. In this study, most of the patients who had heparin-induced thrombocytopenia were men, and most were in the age group of 41 to 60 years. The types of patients receiving anticoagulant therapies and admitted into intensive care units align with these trends [14-16]. Nevertheless, differences in the healthcare system may explain why the absolute numbers here, though almost certainly higher, far eclipse those in other countries. The lack of confirmatory immunoassays, such as the platelet factor 4 antibody test, the dependency on clinical scoring systems, and the inattentive recognition of thrombocytopenia may all explain the findings. The 56.8 percent average platelet count reduction in the patients fit the characteristic diagnostic threshold for heparin-induced thrombocytopenia. The 4Ts scoring system turned out to be a sensible and useful screening method for probable case ascertainment [17]. The average platelet nadir of approximately 118,000/mm³ documented here is in keeping with

other standard descriptions of immune thrombocytopenia, suggesting that the clinical and hematologic profile of the patients in this study is comparable to the profile documented worldwide, except some geographical and resource disparities [18]. This study's results provide the rationale for the anticoagulant monitoring while managing critically ill patients. In the ICU, sepsis is the most common reason for thrombocytopenia. Other potential causes for aspirin induced thrombocytopenia include disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), drug induced marrow suppression, and lack of awareness of serious thromboembolic events [19]. Timely recognition and correct management of heparin induced thrombocytopenia is also the timely substitution of heparin with fondaparinux, argatroban, or bivalirudin, or other suitable anticoagulants. Heparin induced thrombocytopenia (HIT) is characterized by an antibody mediated response against the platelet factor complex. This immune response paradoxically creates a pro thrombotic state which explains thromboses that arise with few platelets [20]. As a result, the mechanism is a large reason HIT needs to be documented, as opposed to simple autoimmunity in these cases. The initial and most important mechanism is the immune response. There is significant evidence that heparin induced thrombocytopenia is a significant problem in tertiary care. There are certainly several notes of caution that to be made here, primarily those of a lack of generalizability. The lack of generalizability is primarily as a result of a small sample that is limited to a single institution. The evaluation of the case relied more on clinical indicators rather than on laboratory test data because of the scarcity of specialized testing, and the 4Ts scoring system, though, is still a valid and reliable screening system, especially in a resource-poor setting.

Conclusion

It is concluded that heparin-induced thrombocytopenia is a significant and relatively frequent complication among critically ill patients receiving unfractionated heparin, with a frequency of

14.7% observed in this study. The higher occurrence may be related to prolonged heparin exposure, severe underlying illness, and limited use of low-molecular-weight heparin in intensive care settings. Most patients developed thrombocytopenia within 5 to 10 days of therapy, indicating the need for vigilant platelet count monitoring and early clinical assessment using tools such as the 4Ts scoring system.

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